

REGULATION OF CELL PROLIFERATION BY TYROSINE PROTEINKINASES RECEPTORS AND THEIR ROLE IN TRIGGERING DIFFERENT TYPES OF CANCERS**Ceban T.,***student, Faculty of General Medicine, SUMPh "Nicolae Testemitanu"
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Chisinau, Republic of Moldova***Abstract**

Receptor tyrosine proteinkinases (RTKs) are transmembrane proteins that possess kinase activity catalyzing the transfer of phosphate groups from ATP to tyrosine residues in protein substrates. RTKs play an important role in the control of most fundamental cellular processes such as proliferation, differentiation, cell metabolism and survival, cell migration and cell cycle control. Tyrosine proteinkinase receptors comprise 58 different types in humans that are classified into 20 families according to structure and ligand. Mutations in RTKs and aberrant activation of their intracellular signalling pathways lead to the triggering of different types of cancers. In human cancers, four fundamental mechanisms have been found to lead to constitutive activation of RTKs: genomic amplification, gain-of-function mutations, chromosomal rearrangements and autocrine activation. Thus, aberrant activation of receptor tyrosine protein kinase is a potential therapeutic target. In recent decades, several drugs, such as tyrosine kinase inhibitors, have been developed and clinically evaluated to improve the survival of cancer patients.

Keywords: receptor tyrosine proteinkinases, mutations, cancer, tyrosine kinase inhibitors.

Cancer is one of the world's biggest problems, both nationally and globally, with around 10 million people dying every year. In 2020, the International Agency for Research on Cancer reported an estimated 19.3 million new cancer cases and 10 million deaths globally, with data from 185 countries. The most commonly diagnosed cancers worldwide were female breast cancer (2.26 million cases), lung cancer (2.21) and prostate cancer (1.41). The most common causes of death among cancers were lung (1.79 million), liver (830,000) and stomach (769,000) cancers. Cancer is a malignant process involving the aberrant development of cells in a tissue with increased potential to invade other parts of the body. In recent decades, tyrosine-pro-

teinases receptors have been widely studied by researchers, as aberrations in their activation or signalling lead to many pathologies, in particular cancers, leading to the development of a variety of drugs that block RTKs signalling and are successfully applied for the treatment of many types of cancers. [3]

Ninety tyrosine kinase genes and five pseudogenes have been identified in the human genome. Of the 90 tyrosine kinases, 58 are receptor tyrosine kinases distributed in 20 subfamilies and 32 are non-receptor tyrosine kinases distributed in 10 subfamilies. The RTK subfamilies are EGFR, InsR, PDGFR, VEGFR, FGFR, PTK7/CCK4, Trk, Ror, MuSK, Met, Axl, Tie, EphA/B, Ret, Ryk, DDR1/2, Ros, LMR, ALK and SuRTK106/STYK1 (Figure1). [8][7][6]

Figure 1. Families of tyrosine protein kinase receptors.[6]

RTKs consist of an extracellular ligand-binding region, a single transmembrane domain and a cytoplasmic tyrosine kinase domain. Notably, the extracellular domain in each receptor class has a different structure and sequence that confers specificity to its ligand and its recognition. The extracellular domain is involved in the dimerization process of the receptor. The transmembrane domain represented by the α -helix consisting of 20 amino acids allows RTK insertion into the cell membrane. This domain plays a key role in dimer formation and stabilization. In the lipid environment of the cell membrane the α -helix is non-covalently oligomerized. Thus, this process preinitiates RTK pre-dimerization in the cell membrane that is able to interact with the corresponding ligand. The cytoplasmic domain includes the tyrosine kinase domain with a small N-terminal lobe that binds ATP and Mg²⁺ and a large C-terminal lobe formed by a carboxyl group (catalytic domain) that contains the activation loop. ATP binds in the cleavage between the two lobes and the tyrosine-containing sequence of the protein substrate, interacts with the residues of the C-terminal lobe and subsequently catalyses the transfer of phosphate groups from ATP to the receptor chains. The N- and C-terminal domains vary between RTK families, reflecting the specificity and diversity of intracellular downstream signals. Binding of a ligand to a receptor causes a change in receptor conformation, known as receptor activation.

After phosphorylation tyrosines or phosphotyrosines then become binding sites for several cytoplasmic proteins. These proteins further activate several downstream signalling pathways, some of the main ones being the MAPK, PI3K, JAK/STAT and PKC pathways. [9][1][4][12]

Abnormal activation of RTK is a complex process involving not only RTK itself, but also adjacent molecules and surrounding environments. Their association with various cellular components further complicates the mechanism of oncogenic RTK activation. Four main mechanisms leading to aberrant activation in human cancers have been proposed, these are: 1) RTK overexpression; 2) gain-of-function mutations; 3) chromosomal translocations and 4) autocrine activation (Figure 2). Overexpression and genomic amplification has been identified in a variety of cancers: EGFR in glioblastoma, esophageal, lung, thyroid cancer; HER2/ErbB2 in breast, bladder, gastric cancer; MET in gastric and lung cancer. Activation by gain-of-function mutations can occur in the extracellular domain, transmembrane domain and juxtamembrane domain of RTK. Point mutations of FGFR3 in the extracellular domain have been reported in cervical carcinomas. HER2 G660D and V659E mutations in the transmembrane domain have been identified in non-small cell lung cancer. KIT V560G and PDGFRA V561D muta-

tions in the juxtamembrane domain are found in gastrointestinal stromal tumours. Chromosomal rearrangements occur in patients with chronic myeloid leukaemia-fusion of the gene encoding tyrosine kinase ABL1 on chromosome 9 with the BCR gene on chromosome 22

Figure 2. Abnormal mechanisms of RTKs activation. [10]

Recently, there has been an increasing focus on developing new and effective drugs that target tumour cells with minimal side effects. For targeted therapies in cancer as ideal representatives are monoclonal antibodies, which compete for the extracellular domain of the receptor, and small molecule inhibitors of tyrosine kinase, which bind to intracellular molecules preventing conformational changes and RTK activation. Currently there are 74 small molecule protein kinase inhibitors approved by the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) as of 12 February 2023. Small molecule tyrosine kinase inhibitors are classified into reversible inhibitors and irreversible inhibitors. Reversible kinase inhibitors are subdivided into four major subtypes based on binding pocket compliance as well as the DFG (ASP-Phe-Gly) motif. Irreversible kinase inhibitors tend to bind covalently and block the ATP site, resulting in irreversible inhibition. Type I inhibitors: bind competitively to the ATP-binding site of active tyrosine kinases. The DFG motif arrangement in type I inhibitors has the aspartate residue facing the catalytic site of the kinase. For example: crizotinib, erlotinib, bosutinib, dasatinib, gefitinib, lapatinib, pazopanib, sunitinib and vemurafenib. Type II inhibitors: bind to inactive kinases, usually at the ATP-binding site. The DFG motif in type II inhibitors is oriented outward, away from the ATP binding site. Due to the outward rotation of the DFG motif, many type II inhibitors can also exploit regions adjacent to ATP binding sites. For example: imatinib, sorafenib, axitinib, nilotinib, ponatinib. Type III inhibitors: do not interact with the

(BCR-ABL). Autocrine activation uses messengers such as growth factors and cytokines. Autocrine activation of different RTKs has been well characterized in various cancers, including HGF-MET, TGF α -EGFR and SCF-KIT autocrine loops. [1][10]

ATP-binding pocket. Type III inhibitors bind exclusively to allosteric pockets adjacent to the ATP-binding region. For example: trametinib, cobimetinib, binitinib. Type IV inhibitors: bind to allosteric sites away from the ATP binding pocket. For example: ON012380, preparation under development. Type V inhibitors: are bivalent inhibitors that bind irreversibly, forming covalent bonds with non-catalytic cysteine residues in the ATP binding pocket. For example: afatinib, ibrutinib, osimertinib. [2][5][13][11]

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